

The Impact of Smoking Cessation Programs on Long-Term Pulmonary Function in Chronic Smokers

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Smoking is a leading cause of chronic respiratory diseases, significantly impairing pulmonary function. Understanding the impact of smoking cessation on long-term pulmonary health is critical for effective treatment strategies.

Objective: This study aims to evaluate the effects of smoking cessation programs on long-term pulmonary function in chronic smokers, focusing on improvements in lung health over time.

Method: Conducted at Teerthanker Mahaveer Medical College and Research Centre, Moradabad, from June 2018 to December 2020, this study involved 234 chronic smokers. Participants were enrolled in a comprehensive smoking cessation program, including behavioural therapy and pharmacotherapy. Pulmonary function tests, including FEV1 and FVC, were administered at baseline, 6 months, and 12 months post-cessation. Statistical analyses were performed to assess changes in lung function and the impact of various cessation strategies.

Results: After 12 months, 78% of participants showed significant improvements in FEV1, with an average increase of 12.5% from baseline ($p < 0.01$). FVC increased by 10.2% in 70% of participants ($p < 0.05$). The overall quit rate was 65%, with participants adhering to both behavioural and pharmacological interventions experiencing the highest improvements. Specifically, 85% of those in the combined intervention group showed notable gains in pulmonary function ($p < 0.01$). Participants with longer smoking durations had a 6.8% smaller average increase in FEV1 compared to those with shorter durations, though improvements remained significant ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Smoking cessation programs significantly enhance long-term pulmonary function in chronic smokers, with substantial improvements observed in FEV1 and FVC. Comprehensive cessation strategies yield the most substantial benefits.

Keywords: Smoking cessation, pulmonary function, chronic smokers, FEV1, smoking interventions.

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Introduction

Smoking remains one of the foremost preventable risk factors for chronic respiratory diseases, with its harmful effects on pulmonary health well-documented across numerous studies [1]. Chronic smokers who have sustained a pattern of tobacco use over extended periods often experience significant impairments in lung function, manifesting as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and other related conditions. Smoking cessation has been recognized as a crucial intervention for improving long-term health outcomes in these individuals. However, the efficacy of smoking cessation programs in enhancing long-term pulmonary function remains a complex and multifaceted issue, necessitating thorough examination and evaluation.

The detrimental effects of smoking on pulmonary function are extensively documented in medical

literature. According to the American Lung Association, smoking causes irreversible damage to the lungs, including a progressive decline in forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1) and an increase in airway inflammation [2]. These changes can lead to chronic bronchitis and emphysema, both classified under the umbrella of COPD (Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease) [3]. Smoking cessation, therefore, is often posited as the most effective strategy to halt or slow the progression of these conditions. Research has demonstrated that smoking cessation can lead to significant improvements in pulmonary function, albeit to varying degrees. A longitudinal study by Leone et al., found that individuals who ceased smoking experienced a stabilization or modest improvement in FEV1 compared to those who continued smoking [4]. This aligns with findings

from a meta-analysis by Ma et al., which highlighted that while the greatest improvements in lung function occur shortly after quitting, the benefits of cessation persist over the long term [5]. The mechanisms through which smoking cessation impacts lung function are multifaceted. On a physiological level, quitting smoking reduces the exposure of lung tissue to harmful toxins and irritants present in tobacco smoke. This reduction in exposure allows the lungs to repair some of the damage incurred during smoking. For instance, smoking cessation has been associated with decreased airway inflammation and improved mucociliary function, which can contribute to better lung function [6]. Moreover, cessation has been linked to a reduction in the rate of decline in FEV1, a key marker of pulmonary health [7]. Despite these benefits, the effectiveness of smoking cessation programs in achieving long-term improvements in pulmonary function can be influenced by various factors. The type of cessation program, individual adherence, and the presence of co-morbid conditions all play critical roles. Comprehensive smoking cessation programs, which incorporate behavioral therapy, pharmacotherapy, and support systems, have shown more substantial long-term benefits compared to less structured interventions [8]. Additionally, the duration of smoking and the degree of existing pulmonary impairment can also affect the extent of improvement post-cessation [9].

However, it is essential to recognize that while smoking cessation yields significant benefits, it does not entirely reverse the damage done by chronic smoking. Long-term smokers may still experience residual pulmonary deficits despite quitting due to the cumulative and irreversible nature of some of the damage caused by smoking [10]. Thus, ongoing monitoring and management of pulmonary health remain crucial even after cessation. Smoking cessation programs are a vital component of public health strategies aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of smoking on pulmonary function. The evidence supports the notion that cessation leads to improvements in long-term lung health, although the degree of improvement can vary based on individual and programmatic factors. Future research should continue to explore the nuances of how different cessation strategies impact pulmonary function over time and identify optimal approaches for maximizing long-term benefits.

Aims and Objectives

This study aims to assess the impact of smoking cessation programs on long-term pulmonary function in chronic smokers. Specifically, it seeks to evaluate improvements in lung health, measured by changes in FEV1 and FVC, and determine the

efficacy of different cessation strategies in enhancing pulmonary outcomes over 12 months.

Material and Methods

Study Design: This longitudinal study was conducted at Teerthanker Mahaveer Medical College and Research Centre, Moradabad, from June 2018 to December 2020. A total of 234 chronic smokers were enrolled and assigned to a comprehensive smoking cessation program, which included behavioral therapy and pharmacotherapy. Pulmonary function was assessed using FEV1 and FVC measurements at baseline, 6 months, and 12 months. Statistical analyses were performed to evaluate changes in lung function and the effectiveness of various cessation interventions.

Inclusion Criteria: Participants included in this study were chronic smokers aged 30 to 65 years with a smoking history of at least 10 pack-years. They had to demonstrate a baseline FEV1 and FVC indicative of compromised pulmonary function, as defined by the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) criteria. Additionally, participants needed to be willing to adhere to a comprehensive smoking cessation program and attend follow-up assessments at 6 and 12 months.

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals were excluded if they had a history of major respiratory illnesses other than chronic bronchitis or emphysema, such as lung cancer or active tuberculosis. Those with significant co-morbid conditions affecting lung function, such as severe heart disease or autoimmune disorders, were also excluded. Additionally, participants who were pregnant, had recent major surgery, or could not comply with the study protocol were excluded to ensure accurate and reliable results.

Data Collection: Data were collected through patient interviews, medical history reviews, and pulmonary function tests. Participants underwent baseline assessments for FEV1 and FVC, followed by follow-up tests at 6- and 12-months post-cessation. Smoking status was confirmed through self-reporting and biochemical verification. Detailed records of adherence to the cessation program, including participation in behavioral therapy and pharmacotherapy, were maintained throughout the study.

Data Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics summarized baseline characteristics and changes in FEV1 and FVC. Paired t-tests assessed differences in lung function from baseline to follow-up, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Chi-square tests evaluated the association between cessation adherence and pulmonary improvements. Multiple regression analysis explored the impact of

smoking duration and intervention type on lung function outcomes, adjusting for potential confounders.

Ethical Considerations: This study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards and received approval from the Institutional Review Board at Teerthanker Mahaveer Medical College and Research Centre. Informed consent was obtained

from all participants, who were fully briefed on the study's objectives, procedures, and potential risks.

Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing data and securely storing all personal information. Participants were assured that they could withdraw from the study without penalty or loss of benefits.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)	p-value
Age			
30-40 years	65	27.8	0.32
41-50 years	92	39.3	
51-65 years	77	32.9	
Gender			
Male	145	62.0	0.07
Female	89	38.0	
Baseline FEV1 < 60%	123	52.6	0.04
Baseline FEV1 ≥ 60%	111	47.4	

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to Sex

The study population was relatively balanced regarding age distribution, with a higher percentage in the 41-50 years category. The majority of participants were male. Significant differences were noted in baseline FEV1 levels, with a higher proportion having values below 60%, indicating compromised pulmonary function at study entry.

Table 2: Smoking History

Variable	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)	p-value
Smoking Duration (10-20 years)	95	40.6	0.15
Smoking Duration (21-30 years)	89	38.0	
Smoking Duration > 30 years	50	21.4	
Average Pack-Years < 20	98	41.9	0.12
Average Pack-Years ≥ 20	136	58.1	

The distribution of smoking duration showed a broad range, with the majority having smoked for 10-20 years or more. The data also indicated that participants with higher pack-year histories had a significant proportion, suggesting heavy smoking was prevalent among the cohort.

Table 3: Adherence to Cessation Program

Variable	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)	p-value
Behavioral Therapy Only	72	30.8	0.03
Pharmacotherapy Only	65	27.8	
Combined Therapy	97	41.4	
Adherence ($\geq 80\%$)	130	55.6	0.01
Adherence ($< 80\%$)	104	44.4	

The combined therapy group, which received both behavioral therapy and pharmacotherapy, showed the highest adherence rates and was associated with the most significant improvements in lung function. Higher adherence to the program was significantly linked to better outcomes, with over half of the participants achieving high adherence levels.

Figure 2: Changes in FEV1

Most participants (77.8%) experienced a significant improvement in FEV1 of 10% or more. No participants showed no improvement, highlighting the effectiveness of the cessation programs in enhancing lung function.

Figure 3: Changes in FVC

Similar to FEV1, 70.1% of participants showed a significant increase in FVC of 10% or more. The improvements were statistically significant, indicating that cessation programs effectively enhanced lung capacity.

Table 4: Quit Rate and Pulmonary Function

Variable	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)	p-value
Overall Quit Rate (≥ 6 months)	152	65.0	0.02
Overall Quit Rate (< 6 months)	82	35.0	
Improvement in FEV1 (quitters)	118	77.6	0.01
Improvement in FEV1 (non-quitters)	60	39.5	

The overall quit rate was 65%, with those quitting for at least 6 months showing significant improvements in FEV1 (77.6%). Non-quitters had lower improvement rates, underscoring the effectiveness of sustained cessation in improving lung function.

Discussion

The results of this study underscore the substantial benefits of smoking cessation programs on long-term pulmonary function in chronic smokers [11,12]. Our findings reveal that 77.8% of participants experienced a significant improvement in FEV1, and 70.1% showed notable increases in FVC after 12 months of quitting. These outcomes are consistent with existing literature, which highlights the positive impact of smoking cessation on lung health. However, our study provides new insights into the effectiveness of comprehensive cessation programs in a specific demographic setting.

The observed improvements in FEV1 and FVC are significant as they align with the primary objective of smoking cessation: halting the progression of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and enhancing lung function. A key finding is that 65% of participants achieved sustained cessation for at least 6 months, a notable rate compared to previous studies. For instance, a meta-analysis by Zhang et al. reported an average quit rate of 50%, with improvements in lung function typically observed within 6 months [13]. Our higher quit rate and pronounced improvements may be attributed to the structured approach of our cessation program, which combined behavioral therapy and pharmacotherapy.

Our study's results agree with those of Deolmi et al., who found that smoking cessation leads to a stabilization or modest improvement in FEV1 [14]. However, our study presents a more pronounced improvement (12.5% increase in FEV1) compared to the average 8% increase reported. This discrepancy might be due to the longer follow-up period in our study and the use of a combined cessation strategy, which is more effective. Similarly, our findings align with those of Stapelberg et al., who demonstrated that comprehensive cessation programs can substantially reduce airway inflammation and improve lung function [15].

Contrasting results can be observed in studies with different demographic or methodological characteristics. For example, a study by Tian et al. involving older adults from European countries reported less pronounced improvements in lung function post-cessation, with average FEV1 increases of around 8% [16]. The differences might be attributed to variations in baseline pulmonary health, smoking duration, or the specific cessation interventions employed. Our study, conducted in a diverse cohort in India, showed robust improvements, potentially due to the high adherence rate and the culturally adapted nature of the cessation program. The significant improvements observed in FEV1 and FVC reinforce the importance of comprehensive smoking cessation programs [17]. This suggests that tailored interventions, combining behavioral and pharmacological approaches, are more effective than singular strategies. The high quit rate and improvement in lung function among our participants underscore the efficacy of such programs in reversing some of the damage caused by chronic smoking.

Moreover, our findings have practical implications for public health strategies. Given the high rate of improvement in lung function, smoking cessation programs should be prioritized and tailored to individual needs to maximize their effectiveness. Healthcare providers should be encouraged to implement and support multifaceted cessation strategies, particularly in high-risk populations.

Comparison and Scientific Evidence

The higher rates of improvement in lung function in our study compared to some international studies may be influenced by several factors. While robust, the sample size of 234 participants is larger than some studies that report more modest improvements, e.g., a study by Creager et al., with 150 participants [18]. Our study's focus on a specific region and demographic could account for differences. Cultural factors, access to health resources, and adherence to cessation programs can vary significantly across regions and populations, affecting overall outcomes.

Racial and country-specific factors also play a role. For example, research by Grigorieva et al. in Western countries may not directly translate to Indian populations due to differences in smoking

behaviors, healthcare infrastructure, and program accessibility [19].

Our findings contribute to the growing evidence that comprehensive cessation programs are universally beneficial but may require adaptation to local contexts to achieve optimal results [20]. Our study provides compelling evidence that comprehensive smoking cessation programs can significantly improve long-term pulmonary function in chronic smokers. The results align with existing literature but highlight the potential for more significant benefits with structured, multifaceted interventions. Further research should continue to explore the effectiveness of cessation programs across diverse populations and settings to refine strategies and enhance global health outcomes.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that comprehensive smoking cessation programs significantly improve long-term pulmonary function in chronic smokers. The substantial increases in FEV1 and FVC observed after 12 months highlight the effectiveness of combining behavioral therapy with pharmacotherapy. These findings support the implementation of multifaceted cessation strategies to enhance lung health and emphasize the potential for reversing smoking-related damage with sustained efforts.

Recommendations

Adopt combined behavioral and pharmacological approaches for smoking cessation.

Ensure these programs are widely accessible, especially in high-risk populations.

Provide continuous follow-up and support to maintain smoking cessation and further improve lung function.

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